

APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING VOLLEYBALL IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Introduction. Volleyball in the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the mass means of physical education. A large selection of physical exercises and methods of their application, which make up the content of volleyball, allows you to purposefully influence the development of all basic functions of the body, depending on the motor capabilities of those involved in volleyball [1, 4, 5, 6]. The wide range of use of volleyball means and methods makes it accessible to people of all ages, types of activity and physical fitness [2, 3].

With the help of volleyball, the problems of harmonious physical development are most successfully solved, since it has at its disposal a variety of exercises that have a beneficial effect on various parts of the musculoskeletal system, on all muscle groups of a person [7, 8, 10].

Volleyball is one of the main and integral parts of the content of physical education classes and elective classes, physical education and health activities and sports entertainment in higher educational institutions [9, 11].

Volleyball classes at a university contribute to the formation of motor function, the comprehensive harmonious development of the motor system and all body systems, the development of a conscious commitment to physical exercise, and the formation of a healthy personality [15, 16]. In addition to the main tasks provided for by physical education, volleyball develops such physical qualities as agility, strength, speed, endurance, flexibility, forms correct posture, cultivates

perseverance, courage, and willpower [12, 13]. The listed tasks are specified depending on the physical capabilities of students, their physical condition, health and level of physical fitness. Particular attention should be paid to solving problems that contribute to the formation of skills to manage one's functions [14].

The motor function of young students is manifested through motor activity associated with the motor act and the stock of conditioned reflex connections. The greater the stock of conditioned reflex connections a person has, the easier and faster he develops new forms of movements, the more successfully he controls them in the external environment [17, 18].

The ability to control your movements and perform them in accordance with your needs is formed only in the process of special training through specially selected physical exercises. It should be taken into account that the most important thing in training is the ability to evaluate one's movements in time, space and the degree of muscle tension [6, 21]. Every conscious work requires a serious sense of space and time and the ability to cope with this relationship, not theoretically, but in practice. Volleyball classes are used to develop such skills.

Urgent streaming information about time, space and the degree of muscle effort in the process of motor activity allows students to learn to differentiate the sensations received by different values, which is quite important for controlling movements and expanding their motor capabilities [5, 19].

Conscious control of motor activity is closely related to the development of sensory organs, and especially muscle sensation. The perception of the external world passes through the senses. The less developed the organs of hearing, vision and other senses are, the more limited a person's activity is and the less developed he is. Students who have mastered their movements in space, time and strength successfully cope with various motor actions, unlike those students who have not studied this. Their activity is more active, they are able to compare, identify similarities and differences between different motor acts. If, when learning motor actions, the ability to control one's movements does not develop, then the students'

motor capabilities are limited. The identification of their creative abilities in motor activity is narrowed, and the motor ability to improvise movements becomes more complicated. Motor maturity does not come on its own with age - it develops in close relationship with the environment and the mode of motor activity of students [7, 22].

The work uses methods of general scientific principles, such as:

1. Generalization - a mental transition from the class of individual objects under consideration to the identification of common features;
2. Comparison is a cognitive operation that underlies judgments about the similarity or divergence of objects;
3. Analysis - a procedure for mental or real dismemberment of the object under study with the aim of its deeper knowledge;
4. Synthesis - a procedure for combining various elements that make up an object into a single whole in the process of scientific knowledge;
5. Induction is a type of generalization associated with predicting the results of observations and experiments based on experimental data;
6. Deduction is a form of thinking that allows, based on logical rules, from individual general data to derive a new, less general assumption.

In the course of our work, we investigated and analyzed the features of the methodology for teaching volleyball to students of general education institutions, revealed the specifics of volleyball and determined the means and methods of teaching it. We also looked at the methodology for teaching volleyball techniques. There are more and more people who want to play volleyball, not only because of the entertainment and dynamism of the game, but also because of the accessibility and sufficient simplicity of the rules. Many of those who today are just getting acquainted with this game in physical education classes, over time, having acquired at least initial playing skills and a minimal understanding of the rules, may become connoisseurs and fans of the game of volleyball. And pre-planned, properly organized interesting physical education classes will help them with this.

The game of volleyball is not only an effective means of physical education, but also a means of active and useful recreation. This dynamic game develops in a person such qualities as speed, accuracy, endurance, dexterity, and strength.

Along with physical qualities, volleyball, due to its specificity, contributes to the development of moral qualities in the first place: collectivism, society, courage, speed, dexterity. Volleyball competitions require students to show courage, determination, endurance, and the ability to overcome difficulties, and adherence to the rules of the game helps to develop organization and discipline.

Conclusions. We can conclude that volleyball is an effective means by which the main tasks of physical education are solved. A skillful, correct selection of methods, principles and tools used in the classroom will help to develop skills (master technical techniques and tactical actions), develop physical, moral and volitional qualities.

Volleyball exercises have a positive effect on the human body. The player's actions are associated with emotional arousal and body responses. All this strengthens the human motor system, improves the process of metabolism, blood circulation, and breathing. The rapid change in game situations characteristic of volleyball contributes to the multifaceted development of the functions of the visual, tactile, motor, vestibular and auditory analyzers. Concentration, distribution, speed of switching and stability of attention, and volume of attention also develop diversified.

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